

Mini-review

Recognition of pain signs in dairy cows

Alice de Boyer Des Roches, Dorothée Ledoux, Isabelle Veissier

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CARE4DAIRY

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1. The issue

Pain is defined as ‘an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with, or resembling that associated with, actual or potential tissue damage (International Association for the Study of Pain -IASP, 2020). IASP states that “Although pain usually serves an adaptive role, it may have adverse effects on function and social and psychological well-being”. Pain must therefore be limited to ensure animal welfare.

In humans, ‘verbal description is only one of several behaviours to express pain; inability to communicate does not negate the possibility that a human or a nonhuman animal experiences pain’ (IASP, 2020). Therefore, non-verbal signs of pain should be sought in animals.

Pain however cannot be detected from the activity of sensory neurons alone because ‘Pain and nociception are different phenomena’. In addition, ‘Pain is always a personal experience that is influenced to varying degrees by biological, psychological, and social factors’ and ‘Through their life experiences, individuals learn the concept of pain’ (IASP, 2020). Thus, similar stimuli are not experienced in the same way by individual animals. It is therefore necessary to decipher behavioural signs or other internal signs resulting from the pain experienced by an animal. This review aims to describe signs of pain that can be recognised by farmers. It focuses on dairy cows and dairy calves.

2. Summary of the scientific knowledge¹

Dairy animals may experience pain during surgical procedures, such as disbudding in calves, or during certain diseases, such as lameness or mastitis in cows. Pain however is not always adequately managed. We believe this is partly due to the lack of adequate recognition of signs of pain. Here, we describe signs of pain that can be recognised by farmers in various situations.

Pain behaviours have been extensively studied in ruminants (Weary et al., 2006; Prunier et al., 2013; Steagall et al., 2021). These behaviours are observed during or after the painful ac and can be grouped into two main categories: changes in spontaneous behaviour (e.g. increased vocalisation, reduced locomotion, changes in body postures and hind limb position, reduced activity, head in a low position and increased attention to the wound), and modification of reactivity e.g. lack of interaction with the environment (Steagall et al., 2021).

¹ The scientific reviews prepared for CARE4DAIRY focused on the literature of the last 10 years (2012-2022), assuming that older articles have already been taken into account in current technical recommendations. Older articles may be cited if they provide complementary knowledge.

2.1. Changes in spontaneous behaviour

Changes in spontaneous behaviour can be identified by farmers during routine observations of cows in their home pen. The farmer may notice a cow that isolates itself from the herd or has an activity that is out of sync with that of other cows. Once the abnormal cow has been identified, close observations of the cow's behaviour provides more detailed information about the pain experienced per se: how the cow moves (locomotion), stands or lies down (postures), etc. Detailed examples are given below.

2.1.1. Social behaviour

When in pain, cattle alter their social behaviours.

Cows suffering from diseases associated with pain (mastitis, pneumonia, metritis) isolate from their conspecifics (Proudfoot et al., 2014). Close observation of dairy cow interactions around an automatic concentrate feeder can also help to identify cows in pain. Indeed, cows in pain show less agonistic interactions around the feeder than healthy cows. This was observed in lame cows (Galindo and Broom, 2000), cows with mastitis (Sepúlveda-Varas et al., 2016), or cows diagnosed the following week with ketosis (Goldhawk et al., 2009) or metritis (Huzzey et al., 2007).

For calves, farmers can focus on social play, which is reduced in the presence of pain: 3 h after thermal dehorning, those that received anaesthetic and analgesic drugs and those not dehorned play more with a social partner than calves dehorned without anaesthesia or analgesia (Mintline et al., 2013).

2.1.2. Play behaviour

When in pain, calves play less.

Locomotor play consists of activities such as running, jumping, or performing rotational body movements (Bekoff and Byers, 1998). When experiencing pain, young animals reduce their locomotor play activity but the results vary depending on the cause of the pain and the species. For example, calves that have been dehorned with caustic paste play less (locomotor play) the day after dehorning than non-dehorned calves (Rushen and de Passillé, 2012). Similarly, calves dehorned with iron without anaesthesia or analgesia play less during the 3 h post procedure than calves that were dehorned with anaesthesia and analgesia (Mintline et al., 2013). Following castration, one-week-old lambs reduce the amount of time they spend playing (Thornton and Waterman-Pearson, 2002), whereas this effect was not observed in one-week-old calves (Molony et al., 1995).

Social play involves two or more individuals responding to each other's actions, such as headbutting, chasing, kicking, overlapping, etc. (Bekoff and Byers, 1998). Three hours after thermal dehorning, calves dehorned without anaesthesia or analgesia played less with a social partner than calves that dehorned with anaesthesia and analgesia or calves not dehorned (Mintline et al., 2013).

2.1.3. Locomotor activity

When in pain, cattle alter their locomotor activity.

When in pain, adult cows walk more: cows stand more when affected by mastitis (Siivonen et al., 2011; Cyples et al., 2012). A similar response is observed in cows experiencing visceral pain induced by rumenotomy (Rialland et al., 2014). In the case of lameness, cows show specific signs. In tethered stalls, cows with a hoof lesion on the hind limb will not bear weight on the affected foot and bear weight unevenly when moving from side to side (Jewell et al., 2021). In loose housing systems, cows avoid bearing weight on the affected foot (Sprecher, 1997).

Calves in pain walk more after dehorning (Faulkner and Weary, 2000; Milligan et al., 2004; Heinrich et al., 2010; Theurer et al., 2012), or castration (for review: (Stafford and Mellor, 2005; Coetzee, 2011)).

2.1.4. Postures

When in pain, cattle adopt postures that limit stimulation of the painful areas.

These postural changes affect the limbs, tail, back, and head carriage. General signs of pain include lowered head and squeezed tail. Postural changes in the back and limb are either pain postures or antalgic postures.

General signs of pain: squeezed tail and lowered head

- **Tail.** During mastitis, cows press their tail against the udder (de Boyer des Roches et al., 2017), as already observed during liver biopsy (Mølgaard et al., 2012) or under LPS-induced systemic (Ledoux et al., 2023) or local (Ginger et al., 2023b) inflammatory pain. On the contrary, cows with dystocia raise their tail for longer (Barrier et al., 2012a).
- **Head.** Cows in pain due to sickness carry their necks low (Gleerup et al., 2015a; de Boyer des Roches et al., 2017). Cows with visceral pain induced by rumenotomy hold more often their head lower the shoulder with the neck held forward (Rialland et al., 2014).

Antalgic posture and pain postures: limbs and back

- **Limbs.** In the case of podal damage, the animal changes its stance when walking (Sprecher et al., 1997; Weary et al., 2006), or when standing (trampling in mastitis (Siivonen et al., 2011)). It changes its lying or standing postures, extending or retracting a limb. Cows with endotoxin-induced mastitis avoid shifting their weight when standing, both with and without lifting their hooves off the ground, particularly at the times when signs of inflammation are most severe (Chapinal et al., 2013).

- **Back.** Cattle with podal pain arch their backs (Sprecher et al., 1997). This posture is specific to podal pain, but can also be observed as an antalgic posture for instance in traumatic reticuloperitonitis (Braun et al., 2020) or after systemic inflammation induced by LPS (Ledoux et al., 2023).

2.1.5. *Standing-lying behaviour*

When in pain, cows change the time spent lying or standing and change their posture less often (e.g. mastitis: de Boyer des Roches et al., 2017).

In fact, the increase or decrease in time spent lying down seems to depend on the type of pain experienced by the cows. Cows were reported to spend more time lying down and less time standing:

- After surgical correction of a displaced abomasum (Newby et al., 2013).
- After claw treatment (Rizk et al., 2012).
- After noxious challenges (application of capsaicin on the skin) (Salzer et al., 2021).
- During clinical metritis (Barragan et al., 2018)

Conversely, cows with systemic inflammation or mastitis, and after a caesarean section or an ovariectomy spend less time lying down and more time standing (see below). The reduced time spent lying may be due to the pain caused by the lying posture itself. Sometimes cows are also restless when lying, which may indicate that cows are having difficulty finding a comfortable position.

- After a systemic inflammatory challenge (intravenous lipopolysaccharide injection), cows spend more time standing up, especially during the night which is usually a preferred time for lying down (Ledoux et al., 2023).
- After surgery (visceral pain provoked by rumenotomy), cows show spontaneous restlessness while lying down: leg stretching, kicking, changing of position without going from lying to standing or from one side to another (Rialland et al., 2014).
- After E. coli LPS challenge in the udder, cows spend less time lying down on the day of the challenge compared with the 2 days before, especially during the 4 to 7 h after LPS infusion (Cycles et al., 2012).
- On day 1 after transrectal palpation/ovariectomy, heifers ovariectomised with or without analgesia spend less time in the sternal recumbent position than control heifers (Lauder et al., 2020).
- Cows receiving pre-caesarean meloxicam spend more time lying down in the 0-8 h and 8-16 h post-caesarean periods than cows receiving placebo (+27.4 and +26.4 min, respectively) and have more lying down bouts in the first 24 h (Barrier et al., 2014).

2.1.6. *Feeding activity*

When in pain, cattle eat and ruminate less.

In many cases of pain, cattle reduce their eating activity. Thus, is the case with mastitis (Zimov et al., 2011; Fogsgaard et al., 2012; Giovannini et al., 2017), after ovariectomy (Lauder et al., 2020), with visceral pain induced by rumenotomy (Rialland et al., 2014), and after a noxious challenge (application of capsaicin) (Salzer et al., 2021) or a systemic LPS challenge (Ledoux et al., 2023). Interestingly, cows spent less time ruminating in the hours following intramammary LPS infusion and more time ruminating later in the day (Fitzpatrick et al., 2013). After surgical correction of left abomasal displacement, dairy cows are less likely to start eating when offered fresh feed, especially if they do not receive pain relief (Newby et al., 2013). A decrease in feed intake can therefore be used to detect pain.

In calves, rumination decreases after castration (Sylvester et al., 2004). In contrast, no change in feeding activity has been shown following disbudding (for a review: Herskin and Nielsen, 2018). Thus, castration and disbudding appear to have different effects on calf activity.

2.1.7. Vocalisations

Some cattle may vocalise when a nociceptive stimulus is applied

It can happen to calves during tagging (Watts and Stookey, 1999) or after disbudding (Caray et al., 2015), but this is not consistently the case (e.g., in cows during biopsy (Mølgaard et al., 2012)).

2.1.8. Facial expression

Facial expression has been studied in rodents (mice (Langford et al., 2010), rats (Sotocinal et al., 2011)) and horses (Dalla Costa et al., 2014; Gleerup et al., 2015b) and to a lesser extent in sheep (McLennan et al., 2016). Few studies address this topic in cattle. When in pain, animals close or open their eyes, purse their lips, clench their teeth, and open or close their nostrils.

2.1.9. Behaviour directed towards the painful area

When in pain, cattle can lick or scratch a painful area.

This has been studied in particular in calves following various painful procedures. For example, after castration, calves lick their scrotum (Molony et al., 1995) and they move their tails more (Robertson et al., 1994). After dehorning, they rub their heads (Morisse et al., 1995) and shake their ears or head (for a review see (Stafford and Mellor, 2005)).

2.1.10. Grooming

Pain is associated with a reduction in time spent grooming.

The effect of pain on grooming behaviour against a support has only been described in models of painful disease or after parturition. Cows with metritis (Mandel et al., 2017) or lameness (Mandel et al., 2018) rub against brushes less often, especially if the brush is far

from the feeder. Similarly, cows with mastitis scratch less against environmental features than healthy cows (Fogsgaard et al., 2012). Assisted calving cows spent less time self-grooming than naturally calving cows, which suggest greater pain (Barrier et al., 2012b).

2.1.11. Maternal care

Whether in pain or not, cows appear to prioritize care of their calf immediately after parturition. For instance, parturition-assisted cows do not take longer to lick the calf and perform as much licking as unassisted dams, suggesting no important delayed onset or impaired expression of maternal behaviour in dams assisted at delivery (Barrier et al., 2012b; Kovács et al., 2016). Similar findings have been obtained in cows with painful diseases (Perier et al., 2019). This means that, if a farmer observes a cow not caring for her calf after parturition, it is likely that the cow suffers seriously.

2.2. Changes in reactivity

Once the farmer has identified a cow that may be in pain, he/she can further test her reactions, e.g. defensive reactions when palpating the painful area, poor appetite even when offered very palatable feed, etc.

2.2.1. Defence response (palpation)

In herbivores, most studies of the effects of painful procedures record withdrawal/defensive behaviour at the time of the procedure.

Defensive responses have been described in calves during disbudding (reviewed by (Herskin and Nielsen, 2018)) or castration (reviewed by Coetzee, 2011, 2013). These procedures induce strong responses: jumps; kicks, etc.

In adult cows, reaction to palpation has been studied during biopsy (Mølgaard et al., 2012), rumenocentesis (Mialon et al., 2012), and ovariectomy (Lauder et al., 2020): cows reactivity increases in relation to pain. After surgery (visceral pain provoked by rumenotomy), the sensitivity to palpation on the leg increases in dairy cows on Days 15 and 21 after surgery: cows were hypersensitive (Rialland et al., 2014)

During mastitis, various reactions have been reported (see below): there is either increased reactivity or equal responsiveness to udder palpation.

- Increased pain sensitivity has been observed in the challenged quarter 6 h after LPS infusion (Fitzpatrick et al., 2013), or during the whole day of challenge (Johnzon et al., 2018); from 1 to 3 days during the engorgement phase between d 1 and 3 after dry off (Bertulat et al., 2017; Skarbye et al., 2018);
- no effect on the response to palpation has been observed after 0.2 µg LPS (from *E. coli*) or of 20 µg LTA (from *S. aureus*) administration (Giovannini et al., 2017).

2.2.2. Defence response at milking

Cows with hyperkeratosis (Cerqueira et al., 2018) or udder inflammation (Medrano-Galarza et al., 2012; Fitzpatrick et al., 2013; Fogsgaard et al., 2015) show more stepping or kicking responses at milking than healthy cows. This has been reported 6 h after intramammary infusion of *E. coli* LPS (Fitzpatrick et al., 2013), and for several days in cows with naturally occurring mastitis milked automatically (Fogsgaard et al., 2015) or in a parlour (Medrano-Galarza et al., 2012).

2.2.3. Response to approach, attention to the surroundings

Cows in pain (either with mastitis or after surgery) are generally less attentive to their surroundings (Gleerup et al., 2015a; de Boyer des Roches et al., 2017; Durand et al., 2021). They are also less motivated to eat when offered fresh food (Ledoux et al., 2023).

2.3. Other signs: clinical signs

Various 'classic' clinical signs can also be used to detect pain in cattle:

- Increase in Rectal Body Temperature (RBT), Heart Rate (HR), and Respiratory Rate (RR)
- Decrease of Rumen Contraction Rate (RCR).

Pain due to udder inflammation is associated with increase of RBT, as demonstrated in experimental mastitis using LPS (Zimov et al., 2011; Fitzpatrick et al., 2013) or entire bacteria (Herry et al., 2017).

Pain is also associated with an increase in HR and RR, as previously shown in several inflammatory diseases (Lehtolainen et al., 2003; Banting et al., 2008), in an experimental capsaicin model (Salzer et al., 2021), in cows with lameness (Bustamante et al., 2015), and in experimental *E. coli* (Herry et al., 2017) or LPS (Waldron et al., 2006) mastitis or under systemic inflammation (Ledoux et al., 2023).

Pain is also associated with a decrease in RCR in cows with LPS mastitis (Zimov et al., 2011), or under systemic inflammation (Ledoux et al., 2023). In traumatic reticuloperitonitis, cows also show spontaneous grunting as a response to pain caused by reticular contractions (Braun et al., 2020).

3. Recommendations

As soon as the cow shows changes in her normal behaviour or clinical vital signs, the farmer should observe her closely for signs of pain.

Table 1 gives an overview of the behavioural signs that can be observed by the farmer at the individual cow level. Signs in red are warnings. If more than one warning is observed, the farmer should call the vet for clinical examination of the cow.

4. Further research needed

Studies should be carried out to distinguish between the various disorders. Behavioural responses are likely to vary with:

- The type of pain (nociceptive vs. neuropathic). Acute nociceptive pain occurs in response to tissue damage and/or inflammation. Neuropathic pain occurs when the somatosensory nervous system itself is damaged.
- The organ: Somatic pain results from damage to the skin, muscles, joints and bones. In humans, it is described as being sharp, stabbing, and highly localised. Visceral pain is associated with damage to visceral tissues. In humans, it is described as being dull, diffuse, and poorly localised.
- Time: Acute pain lasts until tissues recover. Chronic pain persists after tissue recovery.

Validation studies should be carried out to check the relevance of each indicator for the detection of pain (e.g. Tomacheusky et al, 2023). Validation studies need to consider: i) selectivity (i.e. ability to quantify what it is supposed to quantify), which is checked by construct validity (i.e. discrimination between painful vs. pain-free animals) and responsiveness (i.e. discrimination between animals with vs. without analgesic intervention), ii) Reliability, assessed through intra-observer reliability ('repeatability'), and inter-observer reliability ('reproducibility'), and iii) measurement error assessed through specificity (i.e. ability to correctly detect pain-free animals) and sensitivity (i.e. ability to correctly detect animals in pain).

Two decision tools have been developed for cattle: one to assess pain after castration in zebu (de Oliveira et al., 2014) and one to assess pain under naturally occurring medical or surgical pain conditions (Gleerup et al., 2015a). Further research is needed to explore whether these decision tools are sufficiently specific and sensitive to detect pain in various contexts. Such a decision tool would help to decide when to intervene and what to do to alleviate pain.

Table 1. Behavioural signs to be recorded at individual cow level to detect pain. Signs written in red provide warnings. If more than one warning is observed, the vet should be called to carry out a clinical examination of the cow. This grid was developed especially by M. Faure, D. Durand, D. Ledoux and A. de Boyer des Roches

Day:	Hour:	Observer:	Ear Tag Number:	
1. General condition	2. General body posture	3. Posture of the legs: Standing animal	4. Posture of the legs: Lying animal	5. Posture of the back
<input type="checkbox"/> Awake * <input type="checkbox"/> Excited <input type="checkbox"/> Alert <input type="checkbox"/> Sleepy <input type="checkbox"/> Sleeping <input type="checkbox"/> Not responsive <input type="checkbox"/> Other: *neither excited, nor in alert, nor downcast	<input type="checkbox"/> Standing still <input type="checkbox"/> Standing still but unsteady <input type="checkbox"/> Standing still with support on wall <input type="checkbox"/> Standing trampling / waddling <input type="checkbox"/> Sternal recumbency <input type="checkbox"/> Lateral recumbency <input type="checkbox"/> Sitting "doggy position" <input type="checkbox"/> Normal walking <input type="checkbox"/> Unstable walking <input type="checkbox"/> Other:	3.A. Forelimbs: <input type="checkbox"/> Vertical <input type="checkbox"/> Stretched forward / <input type="checkbox"/> Stretched backwards (under A) \ <input type="checkbox"/> Non weight-bearing <input type="checkbox"/> L <input type="checkbox"/> R <input type="checkbox"/> Other: 3.B. Hindquarters: <input type="checkbox"/> Vertical <input type="checkbox"/> To the front (under A) / <input type="checkbox"/> Stretched backwards \ <input type="checkbox"/> Non weight bearing <input type="checkbox"/> L <input type="checkbox"/> R <input type="checkbox"/> Other:	4.A. Forelimbs: <input type="checkbox"/> 2 forelimbs folded <input type="checkbox"/> 2 forelimbs extended <input type="checkbox"/> 1 single forelimb extended <input type="checkbox"/> Other: 4.B. Hindquarters: <input type="checkbox"/> 2 hindquarters folded <input type="checkbox"/> 2 hindquarters extended <input type="checkbox"/> 1 single hindquarter extended <input type="checkbox"/> Other:	If the animal is standing: <input type="checkbox"/> Straight back <input type="checkbox"/> Arched back <input type="checkbox"/> Lordosis <input type="checkbox"/> Back not visible <input type="checkbox"/> Other: If the animal is lying: <input type="checkbox"/> Animal lying down <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
6. Tail posture and movements	7. Head posture*	8. Feeding activity	9. Interaction with the environment	10. Other activities
6.A. Posture: If the animal is standing: <input type="checkbox"/> No support <input type="checkbox"/> Against vulva <input type="checkbox"/> Against vulva and between legs <input type="checkbox"/> Raised <input type="checkbox"/> Not visible <input type="checkbox"/> Other: If the animal is lying: <input type="checkbox"/> Animal lying down <input type="checkbox"/> Not visible <input type="checkbox"/> Other: 6.B. Movements: <input type="checkbox"/> Immobile <input type="checkbox"/> Mobile= touching the lower thighs <input type="checkbox"/> Very Mobile = touching the upper thighs	<input type="checkbox"/> Above the shoulders <input type="checkbox"/> At the shoulders <input type="checkbox"/> Below the shoulders <input type="checkbox"/> Head touching the ground <input type="checkbox"/> Folded on the side <input type="checkbox"/> Not visible <input type="checkbox"/> Other: * for cows standing still	8.A. Behaviour: <input type="checkbox"/> Ruminating / chewing <input type="checkbox"/> Eating <input type="checkbox"/> Drinking <input type="checkbox"/> Licking <input type="checkbox"/> Doesn't eat / ruminate/chew <input type="checkbox"/> Not visible <input type="checkbox"/> Other: 8.B. Food present: <input type="checkbox"/> Hay <input type="checkbox"/> Concentrate <input type="checkbox"/> Straw <input type="checkbox"/> Silage	9.A. Orientation of the head: Head in the corner <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other: 9.B. Movements: <input type="checkbox"/> Mvt of head and ears <input type="checkbox"/> Mvt of head but not of ears <input type="checkbox"/> Mvt of ears but not of head <input type="checkbox"/> No movement <input type="checkbox"/> Not visible <input type="checkbox"/> Other:	<input type="checkbox"/> No other activity Other activity(ies): specify which: <input type="checkbox"/> Licks / sniffs the environment <input type="checkbox"/> Scratching / licking: body part: <input type="checkbox"/> Mufleon a stand <input type="checkbox"/> Self-kicking with hind legs <input type="checkbox"/> Teeth grinding <input type="checkbox"/> Complaints <input type="checkbox"/> Mooring <input type="checkbox"/> Panting or rapid breathing <input type="checkbox"/> Shaking <input type="checkbox"/> Coughing <input type="checkbox"/> Abdomen stretched out <input type="checkbox"/> Abdomen tucked in <input type="checkbox"/> Not visible <input type="checkbox"/> Other:

11. Eyes	12. Muzzle	13. Ears	14. Head muscles	15. Reaction to human presence (after 10s)
<p><u>Opening:</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Wide open <input type="checkbox"/> Open</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Half-open <input type="checkbox"/> Closed</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Bulging eyes <input type="checkbox"/> Not visible</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other:</p> <p><u>Colour (Eye sclera):</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Pink <input type="checkbox"/> Red</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not visible <input type="checkbox"/> Other:</p> <p><u>Enforcement:</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Hollow <input type="checkbox"/> Normal</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not visible <input type="checkbox"/> Other:</p> <p><u>Moisture / Flow:</u></p> <p>Humidity: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>Flow: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Flowing tears</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not visible</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other:</p>	<p><u>Mobility:</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Muzzle movement (snubbing)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No movement (immobile)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not visible</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other:</p> <p><u>Nostrils:</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Contraction of nostrils</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Dilatated nostrils</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Neither dilatation nor contraction</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not visible</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other:</p> <p><u>Moisture / Flow:</u></p> <p>Nasal moisture: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>Nasal discharge: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not visible</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other:</p>	<p><u>Horizontal position:</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Forward <input type="checkbox"/> Middle <input type="checkbox"/> Backward</p> <p><u>Vertical position:</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Up <input type="checkbox"/> Centre <input type="checkbox"/> Down</p> <p><u>Orientation of the auricle:</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Forward <input type="checkbox"/> Backward</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Sideways <input type="checkbox"/> Down</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Ear not visible</p>	<p><u>Muscles of the forehead:</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Prominent</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not prominent</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not visible</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other:</p> <p><u>Brow bone (above the eyes):</u></p> <p>Prominent: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>Flattened: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not visible</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other:</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Immobile, observing</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Immobile, indifferent</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Approaching but no contact</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Approaching and contact (muzzle, tongue)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Walks backward</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Flee</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Attacks</p> <hr/> <p>16. Reaction to a feeding motivation test</p> <p><u>Feed used in the test:</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Concentrate</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Hay</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Silage</p> <p><u>Reaction of the animal:</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Comes and eats</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Comes but does not eat</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Does not come</p>

5. Literature search

Search made Feb 21 2022

Search equation in WOS:

- Topic: pain AND (cattle or cow or cows or calf or calves or heifer?) AND (sign? or indicator?)
- Years: from 01/01/2021 to 30/06/2022

note: symptom was not included in the equation because too often associated with clinical symptoms of a disease and not to symptoms of pain, resulting in wrong selection of paper.

Number of results: 247

Selection process:

No. publications excluded	Reasons for exclusion
97	Not on cattle (incl. buffalo)
66	Not addressing a painful condition
20	Not addressing signs of pain or using signs of pain not accessible to farmers (e.g. neuro-hormonal concentrations)

64 left with

- 42 papers dealing with pain in calves due to surgery (disbudding: 10 papers; castration, 27 papers)
- 22 papers dealing with pain in cows or heifers → focus for the present review

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